

http://plugin53.marketingdigitaltools.com/

NOVO TESTE

```

Search | <!doctype html>(Use /re/ syntax for regexp search)
2       <html lang="pt-PT">
3
4       <head>
5           <meta charset="UTF-8">
6           <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, in
7           <link rel="profile" href="http://gmpg.org/xfn/11">
8
9       <title>Marketing Digital Tools &#8211; Agência de Mar
10 <link rel='dns-prefetch' href='//s.w.org' />
11 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
12 <link rel="alternate" type="application/rss+xml" title="Market
13     <script type="text/javascript">
14         window._wpemojiSettings = {"baseUrl":"https:\\/\\/s.
15         !function(e,a,t){var r,n,o,i,p=a.createElement("ca
16     </script>
17     <style type="text/css">
18     img.wp-smiley,
19     img.emoji {
20         display: inline !important;
21         border: none !important;
22         box-shadow: none !important;
23         height: 1em !important;
24         width: 1em !important;
25         margin: 0 .07em !important;
26         vertical-align: -0.1em !important;
27         background: none !important;
28         padding: 0 !important;
29     }
30 </style>
31     <link rel='stylesheet' id='wp-block-library-css' href='ht
32 <link rel='stylesheet' id='wc-block-style-css' href='http://g
33 <link rel='stylesheet' id='dashicons-css' href='http://plugi
34 <link rel='stylesheet' id='everest-forms-general-css' href='h
35 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-layout-css' href='http
36 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-smallscreen-css' href=
37 <link rel='stylesheet' id='woocommerce-general-css' href='htt
38 <style id='woocommerce-inline-inline-css' type='text/css'>
39 .woocommerce form .form-row .required { visibility: visible; }
40 </style>
41 <link rel='stylesheet' id='font-awesome-css' href='http://pl
42 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-style-css' href='http://plug
43 <style id='zakra-style-inline-css' type='text/css'>
44 @media (min-width: 1200px) { .tg-container{max-width: 1200px;}
45 .tg-primary-menu > div ul li a{font-family: -apple-system, bli
46 </style>
47 <link rel='stylesheet' id='zakra-woocommerce-style-css' href=
48 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-css' href='http://
49 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-animations-css' href='ht
50 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-frontend-css' href='http
51 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-global-css' href='http://
52 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-post-24-css' href='http:
53 <link rel='stylesheet' id='google-fonts-1-css' href='https://
54 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-shared-0-css' href
55 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-fa-solid-css' href
56 <link rel='stylesheet' id='elementor-icons-fa-brands-css' hre
57 <script type='text/javascript' src='http://plugin53.marketingd
58 <script type='text/javascript' src='http://plugin53.marketingd
59 <link rel='https://api.w.org/' href='http://plugin53.marketing
60 <link rel="EditURI" type="application/rsd+xml" title="RSD" hre
61 <link rel="wlwmanifest" type="application/wlwmanifest+xml" hre
62 <meta name="generator" content="WordPress 5.3.2" />
63 <meta name="generator" content="Everest Forms 1.5.10" />
64 <meta name="generator" content="WooCommerce 3.9.1" />
65 <link rel="canonical" href="http://plugin53.marketingdigitalto
66 <link rel="shortlink" href="http://plugin53.marketingdigitalto
67 <link rel="alternate" type="application/json+oembed" href="ht
68 <link rel="alternate" type="text/xml+oembed" href="http://
69 <!-- Markup (JSON-LD) structured in schema.org ver.4.7.0 S
70 <script type="application/ld+json">
    
```

Detetada ProfessionalService 0 ERROS 0 AVISOS 7 ITENS

OrganizationalService	PRÉ-	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
@type	ProfessionalService			
BreakerItemList	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM	
	Marketing Digital Tools			
	http://plugin01.marketingdigitaltools.c			
WebSiteImage	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM	
	om/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Elogo			
	Marketing-Digital-Tools-com-			
ProfessionalService	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM	
url	http://plugin53.marketingdigitaltools.c			
	om/			
SiteNavigationElement	+351913824934	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM	
openingHours	Mo-Fr 09:00-18:00			
priceRange	250€-2000€			
Personaddress	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM	
@type	PostalAddress			
BlogPostingstreetAddress	Rua de Santo António de Centumil, 651			
addressLocality	Porto			
postalCode	4350-291			
addressRegion	Porto			
addressCountry				
@type	Country			
name	Portugal			
geo				
@type	GeoCoordinates			
latitude	41.173869			
longitude	-8.580057			